

Milestone/Deliverable
Responsible Beneficiary

D 6.2
UNIPD

Training activities from M8 to M19
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Training activities from M8 to M19

What	Organizer / Co-organizer	Duration	When	Mode	Main reference
First Annual meeting	UNIPD	2 days	Nov 30 th – Dec 1 st , 2021	On-line	Stefano Grigolato / Paolo Carlucci
Forest dynamics (webinar)	TUM/SGGW/PFD	2 hours	Jan 14 th 2022	On-line	Hans Pretzsch / Kamil Bielak
The impact of climate change on forests: a physiological approach (webinar)	INIA/AGRESTA	2 hours	Jan 18 th 2022	On-line	Marta Pardos / Jorge Olivar
Training in intercultural communication and languages (softskill)	TUM BAYFOR	Half day	Feb 22 th 2022 (morning)	On-line	Enno Uhl / Carolin Schuback
Carbon cycle in forest (webinar)	UNIBZ AGRESTA	2 hours	Feb 22 th 2022 (afternoon)		Camill Wellstein / Jorge Olivar
Use of LIDAR technologies in innovative assessment of forest resources (2 days) (Applied Training)	UVA/FORA/AGRESTA	2 days	March 7 th -11 th 2022	ES	Felipe Bravo / Inigo Lizzaralde
Carbon cycle evaluation in forestry: how to measure carbon in forests and data analysis (2 days) (Applied Training)		2 days			Marta Pardos / Jorge Olivar
Diffusing research results to consulting companies/innovation in forest business (softskill)	UVA FORA	2-3 hours	March 1 st 2022	On-line	Felipe Bravo / Inigo Lizzaralde
Carbon emission evaluation in forestry (webinar)	UNIPD	2 hours	Sept 23 th , 2022	On-line	Stefano Grigolato